

密级

硕士学位论文

**HYPERURICEMIA PROMOTES PROGRESSION OF Ig A
NEPHROPATHY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-
ANALYSIS**

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HYPERURICEMIA PROMOTES PROGRESSION OF Ig A NEPHROPATHY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

Abstract

Background; Considered as the most common type of glomerulonephritis worldwide, Ig A nephropathy (IGAN) is a very significant cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD).10%-20% of patients will most probably develop ESRD in the first 10 years after diagnosis. There are numerous risk factors associated with poor prognosis in IGAN; heavy proteinuria, renal impairment at the time of diagnosis or renal biopsy, hypoalbuminemia, male gender, hypertension, age below 30 years. More recently *hyperuricemia* has gained much attention because of its possible role in aggravation of IGAN. IGAN progression is considered when there is an increase in nitrogenous waste products (blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine), increase in proteinuria, a deterioration in blood pressure (either diastolic and/or systolic blood pressure) and when more severe pathological features are associated (namely degree of mesangial proliferation glomerulosclerosis and tubulointerstitial nephritis).There have been several interesting studies assessing the effect of hyperuricemia on the progression of IgA nephropathy (IGAN). Some studies have shown a positive impact on the progression of IGAN whereas results of other studies differed from previous ones. But how far does this hyperuricemia affects IGAN is still unclear. Therefore, we cautiously carried out a meta-analysis to investigate the effect of elevated uric acid on IGAN progression. **Methods;** we searched multiple electronic databases [(PubMed/Medline, OVID evidence based- medicine, ClinicalKey, Chinese Biomedical Literature and Chinese science and technological periodicals (CNKI)] for studies published from January 1980 until October 2015. The inclusion criteria were case-control, cohort studies published in any language. The following free text words were used: Ig A nephropathy, Ig A glomerulonephritis, Berger's disease, uric acid, hyperuricemia, allopurinol, oxypurinol, febuxostat, and progression. The quality of papers was assessed by the Jadad scoring system. A score ≥ 3 is considered of good quality. The papers were

selected based on their design of study, contents and titles. The studies needed to have a normouricemic and a hyperuricemic group. IGAN was proven by renal biopsy. We conducted a sensitive analysis to assess the relationship between hyperuricemia and IGAN. Statistical significance was achieved if $p < 0.05$. We assessed the heterogeneity in studies using the X^2 statistic (with substantial heterogeneity defined as values $> 50\%$).

Results; The final analysis included 11 studies (retrospective) with a total of 2014 patients.

a) **Blood urea nitrogen (BUN)**

There were 5 studies, with 465 patients assessing the increase in BUN. The Meta-analysis showed that there was a significant increase in BUN hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 2.83% 95%CI: 2.48-3.18, $p < 0.00001$: heterogeneity $X^2=8.63$, $I^2=54\%$, $p=0.07$).

b) **Serum creatinine level**

Analysis of 6 studies (involving 726 patients) achieved a significant increase in serum creatinine hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 4.49% 95%CI: 2.09-6.93, $p=0.003$; heterogeneity $X^2=8.02$, $I^2=38\%$, $p=0.16$).

c) **Diastolic blood pressure**

441 patients enrolled in an analysis of 4 studies revealed a significant increase in diastolic blood pressure in hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 1.5% 95%CI: 0.08-2.93, $p=0.04$; heterogeneity $X^2=0.64$, $I^2=0\%$, $p=0.73$).

d) **Systolic blood pressure**

Similarly, a significant increase in systolic blood pressure of hyperuricemic IGAN patients was proven in a meta-analysis of 3 studies of 541 patients (MD 3.55% 95%CI: 1.67-5.43, $p=0.0002$ heterogeneity $X^2=7.65$, $I^2=74\%$, $p=0.02$). Sensitive analysis using a random model in this group revealed the following results; Tau^2 9.29, $X^2=7.65$, $I^2=74\%$ $p=0.02$, MD 3.40, 95%CI: -0.75-7.56 $p=0.11$.

e) 24-hour urine protein

Analysis of studies regarding 24 hour urine protein involved two subgroups: 1st group having 5 studies and 1227 patients and 2nd group having 5 studies and 436 patients. Both subgroups show significant increase in 24 hour urine protein in the hyperuricemic IGAN patients, [(group 1-MD 0.5%,95% CI 0.41-0.61, p=0.00001; heterogeneity $X^2=2.53$, $I^2=0\%$, p=0.64), (group 2- MD 1.2%,95% CI 1.06-1.37, p<0.00001; heterogeneity $X^2=8.25$, $I^2=52\%$, p=0.08).

Pathologically, the hyperuricemic IGAN patients had **significant increase in**

f) Mesangial proliferation

3 studies, 890 patients MD 0.09% 95%CI: 0.02-0.16, p<0.01; heterogeneity $X^2=0.93$, $I^2=0\%$, p=0.63,

g) Glomerulosclerosis

3 studies, 943 patients MD 0.31% 95%CI: 0.27-0.36, p<0.00001; heterogeneity $X^2=7.43$, $I^2=73\%$, p=0.02,

h) Tubulointerstitial nephritis

4 studies 493 patients MD 1.29% 95%CI: 1.25-1.34, p<0.00001; heterogeneity $X^2=6.79$, $I^2=56\%$, p=0.08

Conclusions; after our meta-analysis we found that hyperuricemia is associated with a higher degree of mesangial proliferation, a more severe glomerulosclerosis, and enhanced tubulointerstitial nephritis. Moreover, hyperuricemia is also linked with increased level blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine, greater diastolic and systolic blood pressure and a higher grade of proteinuria. It can also be concluded that hyperuricemia promotes the clinical and pathological progression of Ig A nephropathy.

Keywords: IgA nephropathy Hyperuricemia Prognosis of Ig A nephropathy Meta-analysis

血尿酸对 IgA 肾病进展的促进作用：系统回顾与 Meta 分析

摘要

背景 IgA 肾病是最常见的肾小球肾炎，同时也是终末期肾脏病的常见原发病。10-20% 的 IgA 肾病患者在诊断后 10 年会发展成为终末期肾脏病。目前发现有很多导致 IgA 肾病预后不良的危险因素：大量蛋白尿，诊断或肾穿刺活检时已经出现肾功能损害，高血压，男性，30 岁以下。体内含氮代谢产物（血肌酐、尿素氮）的增多、蛋白尿的增加、血压上升（舒张压和/或收缩压）、更严重的肾脏病理特征（一定程度的系膜增生性肾小球硬化和肾小管间质性肾炎）。最近，高尿酸血症是否导致 IgA 肾病预后不良备受关注。目前有些对于高尿酸血症在 IgA 肾病进展中作用的研究。部分研究认为高尿酸血症促进了 IgA 肾病的进展，部分研究不支持该观点。但是高尿酸血症对于 IgA 肾病进展的影响程度还不清楚。因此我们进行了这项 Meta 分析以评估高尿酸对 IgA 肾病进展的影响。

方法 我们搜索了多个数据库（PubMed/Medline，OVID evidence based- medicine，ClinicalKey，中国生物医学文献和中国科学技术期刊（CNKI））在 1980 年 1 月至 2015 年 1 月期间发表的文章。纳入各国语言发表的病例对照和队列研究。研究包括正常血尿酸组和高尿酸血症组。研究中的 IgA 肾病皆由穿刺活检确诊。我们进行了敏感性分析，探讨高尿酸血症对 IgA 肾病的影响。如果 $P < 0.05$ ，则有统计学意义。我们在研究中运用 X^2 检验来评估差异性（高异质性为值 $> 50\%$ ）。

结果 最终纳入 11 项研究（回顾性），一共 2014 名患者。其中有 5 项研究，共 465 例检测到血尿素氮（BUN）升高。Meta 分析显示，伴高尿酸血症的 IgA 肾病患者 BUN 升高明显（MD 2.83%，95% 可信区间：2.48-3.18， $P < 0.00001$ ；异质性 $X^2 = 8.63$ ， $I^2 = 54\%$ ， $P = 0.07$ ）。6 项研究（包括 726 例患者）分析结果显示，伴高尿酸血症的 IgAN 患者血肌酐明显升高（MD 4.49%，95% 可信区间：2.09-6.93， $P = 0.003$ ；异质性 $X^2 = 8.02$ ， $I^2 = 38\%$ ， $P = 0.16$ ）。包含 441 例患者的 4 项研究分析结果示，伴

高尿酸血症的 IgAN 患者舒张压显著升高 (MD 1.5%, 95%可信区间: 0.08-2.93, $P = 0.04$; 异质性 $X^2 = 0.64$, $I^2 = 0\%$, $P = 0.73$)。同样, 出现收缩压显著升高的 3 项研究共 541 例患者的荟萃分析也表现出有统计学差异 (MD 3.55%, 95%可信区间: 1.67-5.43, $P = 0.0002$ 异质性 $x = 7.65, I^2 = 74\%$, $P = 0.02$)。对采用随机分组的研究模型进行敏感性分析结果表明: $Tau^2 = 9.29$, $X^2 = 7.65$, $I^2 = 74\%$, $P = 0.02$, MD 3.40, 95%可信区间: -0.75-7.56, $P = 0.11$ 。有关 24 小时尿蛋白两个分组的研究分析显示: 第一组由 5 个研究共 1227 例、第二组有 5 个研究 436 例患者。两组高尿酸血症 IgAN 患者的 24 小时尿蛋白均明显增加[(组 1- MD 0.5%, 95%可信区间 0.41-0.61, $P = 0.00001$; 异质性 $X^2 = 2.53$, $I^2 = 0\%$, $P = 0.64$) , (组 2-MD 1.2%, 95%可信区间 1.06-1.37, $P < 0.00001$; 异质性 $X^2 = 8.25$, $I^2 = 52\%$, $P = 0.08$)]。有关病理改变上的分析结果显示: 伴高尿酸血症 IgAN 的患者发生肾小球系膜增生 (3 项研究共 890 例) (MD 0.09%, 95%可信区间: 0.02-0.16, $P < 0.01$; 异质性 $X^2 = 0.93$, $I^2 = 0\%$, $P = 0.63$)]; 发生肾小球硬化症 (3 项研究中, 共 943 例患者) (MD 0.31%, 95%可信区间: 0.27-0.36, $P < 0.00001$; 异质性 $X^2 = 7.43$, $I^2 = 73\%$, $P = 0.02$)], 发生肾小管间质性肾炎 (有 4 项研究, 共 493 例患者) (MD 1.29%, 95%可信区间: 1.25-1.34, $P < 0.00001$; 异质性 $X^2 = 6.79$, $I^2 = 56\%$, $P = 0.08$)]。

结论本: meta 分析发现 IgA 肾病患者的高尿酸血症与系膜细胞增生, 肾小球硬化和肾小管间质肾炎的严重程度相关, 与 IgA 肾病患者的血尿素氮、血肌酐的升高相关, 与患者的高血压及蛋白尿程度相关

关键词 IgA 肾病 高尿酸血症 IgA 肾病的预后 Meta 分析

1. Introduction

Being the most common type of glomerulonephritis worldwide, Ig A nephropathy (IGAN) is a very significant cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) ^[12]. 10%-20% of patients will most probably develop ESRD in the first 10 years after diagnosis.^[12]IGAN is an autoimmune disease with a known antigen, galactose-deficient IgA1, which can show an antigen-antibody response leading to formation of autoimmune complexes and their subsequent deposition in the mesangial area.

There are numerous risk factors associated with poor prognosis in IGAN; heavy proteinuria, renal impairment at the time of diagnosis or renal biopsy, hypoalbuminemia, male gender, hypertension, age below 30 years. More recently *hyperuricemia* has gained much attention because of its possible role in aggravation of IGAN. It is speculated that IGAN patients with hyperuricemia have worse clinical and pathological prognosis.

Uric acid mediates its effect by inhibition of nitric oxide synthase leading to a decreased level of nitric oxide and hence endothelial dysfunction ^[13] Increased serum uric acid causes kidney vasoconstriction and activation of the renin-angiotensin system ^[11]

There are several studies that have which have assessed this issue of hyperuricemia on IGAN. Many studies have shown significant relationships between serum uric acid and tubular atrophy, interstitial fibrosis and inflammation, proteinuria and glomerulosclerosis ^[14, 15, and 16]. Other study did not show the direct influence of hyperuricemia on the pathological features of IGAN ^[17].The aim of this meta-analysis is to establish more clearly the effects of elevated uric acid on the progression of IGAN.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 *Study protocol*

We have carried out a systematic review and meta-analysis according to a previously published protocol (<http://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPERO>).

2.2 Search strategy

We have used the following terms for standard medical subject headings and free text words: Ig A nephropathy, Ig A glomerulonephritis, Berger's disease, immunoglobulin A nephropathy, uric acid, hyperuricemia, allopurinol, oxypurinol, febuxostat, and progression. Our search was restricted to studies in humans from January 1980 to October 2015. We used these electronic databases; PubMed/Medline, OVID evidence based- medicine, ClinicalKey, Chinese Biomedical Literature and Chinese science and technological periodicals (CNKI). Moreover, we searched other potentially significant and relevant studies by using a manual of search of references from all eligible studies, review articles, and also searched through the 'related articles' feature of PubMed. Three searchers conducted the search independently. If one of the searchers thought that the article was appropriate, the study was selected. Articles, other than in English language were duly and carefully translated. The translations were verified by another person and, where necessary, corrections were made.

2.3 Study selection

The inclusion criteria were case-control, cohort studies (prospective or retrospective) published. The included studies needed to have a comparison between groups of normouricemic and hyperuricemic IGAN patients. IGAN should be proven by biopsy. IGAN progression was considered when there was, at least, deterioration in renal dysfunction, an increase in proteinuria, a deterioration in blood pressure (either diastolic and/or systolic blood pressure) and presence of when more severe pathological features. Exclusion criteria included (1) no description of primary or secondary outcomes (2) patients with secondary IGAN and (3) IGAN patients on uric acid lowering treatment.

2.4 Data extraction and statistical analysis

Data were extracted by three different authors independently using standard data extraction forms. Where more than one publication of one study exists, reports were assembled together and only the publication with the most complete data was included. Mean difference (MD) and 95% confidence intervals were used to analyse the continuous data.

Heterogeneity between studies was tested using the X^2 test. The size of heterogeneity in the included studies was assessed using I^2 . All the analyses were performed using the Review Manager 5.3 (The Nordic Cochrane Centre). Analysis was clinically significant if $p < 0.05$.

2.5 Outcome assessment

Primary outcome of this analysis was deterioration in kidney function, characterized by increase in blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine. Secondary outcomes are increase in 24 hour urine protein, worsening of blood pressure and appearance of more severe pathological features, like degree of mesangial proliferation and glomerulosclerosis and tubulointerstitial nephritis.

2.6 Quality assessment

The study quality was determined with a Jadad composite score, which is 5 point quality scale with the lowest being 1 and highest being 5. A study has been defined as high quality scale study if it has a Jadad score ≥ 3 . Publication bias was assessed using the funnel plot technique ^[18].

Figure 1. Structure of paper reviewed

Table 1 Main characteristic of included studies

Papers	Design	Sample Size	Nationality	Year	Jadad score
TIAN YUN [1]	Cohort study	311	Chinese	2012	3
SHEN SHI ZHONG [2]	Cohort study	110	Chinese	2013	2
XING DE LIU [3]	Cohort study	32	Chinese	2012	2
LIU CUI [4]	Cohort study	92	Chinese	2011	3
GAO XUE YAN [5]	Cohort study	542	Chinese	2013	2
CAI LU [6]	Cohort study	109	Chinese	2014	2
CUI MING JI [7]	Cohort study	148	Chinese	2011	2
SU-JI KIM [8]	Cohort study	193	Korean	2012	3
BAKAN ALI [9]	Cohort study	93	Turkish	2015	3
LIAN XI YAN [10]	Cohort study	126	Chinese	2010	2
GEN –YANG CHENG [11]	Cohort study	348	Chinese	2013	2
Total		2014			

Table 2. Features of different papers

Papers	Design	Sample size	Events	Analysis	Follow-up (year)	Age (year)
TIAN YUN [1]	Cohort study	311	149	a) number of patients with different pathological features according to Lee's classification b)24 hour urine protein c)serum creatinine level	January 2009-january 2010 (1)	35.9±11.6

SHEN SHI ZHONG [2]	Cohort study	110	55	a)different degrees of -mesangial proliferation, -glomerular sclerosis, -tubulointerstitial nephritis [by Katafuchi Score] b)level of blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine c)24 hour urine protein d)diastolic and systolic blood pressure	December 1998-June 2011 (12.5)
XING DE LIU [3]	Cohort study	32	15	a)quantity of -mesenchymal fibrosis -tubular atrophy -presence or absence crescent formation -arterial wall thickening -inflammatory cell infiltrate b) level of blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine c) level of 24 hour urine protein d)diastolic blood pressure and systolic blood pressure	March 2008- March 2010 (2)	33.9±9.2
LIU [4]	CUI Cohort study	92	26	a)different degrees of -mesangial proliferation, -glomerular sclerosis, -tubulointerstitial nephritis [by Katafuchi Score] b)level of blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine c)24 hour urine protein d)diastolic and systolic blood pressure	Age group 17-60 yrs 35.32±11.15

GAO XUE YAN [5]	Cohort study	542	171	a) level of Serum creatinine b)) level of 24 hour urine protein c) score of different pathological features according to Lee's classification	2008-2012 (4)	Age group 15-71
CAI LIU [6]	Cohort study	109	41	a)24 hour urine protein b)serum creatinine c)number of patients with hypertension d)number of patients with -glomerulosclerosis -crescent formation -tubular fibrosis -interstitial fibrosis	June 2004- June 2013 (9)	Age group 19-64 35.87±8.65
CUI MING JI [7]	Cohort study	148	41	a)serum albumin b)level of blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine c)24 hour urine protein d)lipid profile (total cholesterol, HDL, LDL) e)number of patients with different pathological features according to Lee's classification	January 2007- December 2010 (4)	37±13
SU-JI KIM [8]	Cohort study	193	50	a)level of blood urea nitrogen b)level of serum creatinine c)systolic blood pressure d)diastolic blood pressure e)24 hour urine protein	January 1999- December 2005 (6)	34.99±12.14

BAKAN ALI [9]	Cohort study	93	30	a)systolic blood pressure (interquartile range) b)diastolic blood pressure ($\bar{x}\pm s$) c)body mass index d) Lipid profile (total cholesterol, HDL. LDL) e) level of serum creatinine f)calcium level g)phosphorus level h) serum albumin level	44.3±12.4
LIAN XI YAN [10]	Cohort study	126	39	i) hemoglobin level a)level of systolic blood b) 24 hour urine protein level c) Lipid profile (total cholesterol, HDL. LDL) d) diastolic blood pressure level e) number of patients with different pathological features according to Lee's classification	January 1998- January 2008 (10)	Age group 17-68 35±12
GEN YANG CHENG [11]	Cohort study	348	66	a)level of systolic pressure b)level of diastolic blood pressure c)level of serum creatinine and blood urea creatinine d) 24 hour urine protein e) serum albumin level	May 2001- July 2009 (8+2months)	34.29±8.18
TOTAL		2014	683			

3 Results

3.1 Selection and description of studies

We included 11 studies in our meta-analysis (cohort studies) involving 2014 patients (minimum 32 and maximum 542). Duration of studies was from 1 year to 13 years. Nine studies were from China and one study from Turkey and the last one from South Korea. Almost all of the studies were conducted using Asian population. One reason is that the incidence of IGAN is higher in Asia than other continents ^[19]. We analyzed the effect of hyperuricemia on different clinical and pathological features in IGAN patients. All the 11 included studies showed that hyperuricemia is associated with either more severe clinical and/or pathological features.

It is worth to note that Liu Cui et al. ^[10] analyzed the comparison between normouricemic and hyperuricemic in two sets of patients; one with normal renal function and another one with renal dysfunction. Similarly, Gen Yang Cheng et al. ^[11] also analyzed two sets of patients; one with normal eGFR and the other one with low eGFR.

3.2 Relationship between hyperuricemia and BUN

At first analysis of 9 studies, with a 1032 patients, assessing elevation of blood urea nitrogen (BUN) showed that there was a significant increase in BUN hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 0.89% 95%CI: 0.72-1.06, $p < 0.00001$: heterogeneity $X^2=282.68, I^2=97%$, $p < 0.00001$; fig 2). We used a fixed model instead of a random effects model which did not change our initial results. Sensitivity analysis excluding each individual study at a time was similar in the direction and analysis of similar estimates. But because of the big heterogeneity among the studies we selected a subgroup of 5 studies (465) with having almost similar characteristics (being more homogeneous) and we found out that in this subgroup also there was a significant increase in the BUN in hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 2.83% 95%CI: 2.48-3.18, $p < 0.00001$: heterogeneity $X^2=8.63, I^2=54%$, $p=0.07$, fig 3). This subgroup is considered as our final result (MD 2.83% 95%CI: 2.48-3.18, $p < 0.00001$ favours hyperuricemia) concerning effect of hyperuricemia on BUN.

Figure 2. Comparison between normouricemic and hyperuricemic IGAN patients in terms of BUN increase.

Fig 3. Subgroup analysis: Comparison between normouricemic and hyperuricemic IGAN patients in terms of BUN increase.

Figure 4. Funnel plot of the mean differences in BUN versus standard errors of the mean differences of the studies that assessed the effect of hyperuricemia in BUN.

3.3 Relationship between hyperuricemia on serum creatinine

Initial analysis of 12 studies (involving 1978 patients) achieved a significant increase in serum creatinine between the two groups of IGAN patients [(MD 16.30% 95%CI: 14.11-18.48, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=520.06$, $I^2=98\%$, $p < 0.00001$); fig 5]. We used a fixed model instead of a random effects model which did not change our initial results. Sensitivity analysis excluding each individual study at a time was similar in the direction and analysis of similar estimates. Because of heterogeneity, some low grade studies and some studies having non similar mean differences were excluded. Hence a subgroup of 6 studies involving 726 students was analyzed. This subgroup meta-analysis also showed that there was a significant increase in the serum creatinine among hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 4.49% 95%CI: 2.09-6.93, $p=0.003$; heterogeneity $X^2=8.02$, $I^2=38\%$, $p=0.16$, fig 6). The analysis of this subgroup is considered our final result (MD 4.49% 95%CI:

2.09-6.93, p=0.003: favours hyperuricemia). Fixed model analysis was used and further sensitive analysis excluding each individual study at a time was similar in the direction and analysis of similar estimates.

Figure 5. Forrest plot comparison in terms of serum creatinine

Figure 6. Subgroup analysis: Forrest plot comparison in terms of serum creatinine

Figure 7. Funnel plot of the mean differences in serum creatinine versus standard errors of the mean differences of the studies that assessed the effect of hyperuricemia in serum creatinine

3.4 Relationship between hyperuricemia and 24-hour urine protein

Hyperuricemia IGAN patients, following an analysis of 12 studies with 1993 patients, were associated with a significant increase in 24 hour urine protein (MD 0.56% 95%CI: 0.48-0.63, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=125.62$, $I^2=91\%$, $p < 0.00001$, fig 8). In this case also, fixed model analysis was used and further sensitive analysis excluding each individual study at a time was similar in the direction and analysis of similar estimates. For further analyses we created two subgroups of 5 studies each, 1st subgroup having 1227 patients and 2nd subgroup having 436. The results are as follows: ,subgroup 1-MD 0.5%,95% CI 0.41-0.61, $p=0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=2.53$, $I^2=0\%$, $p=0.64$,fig 6.2, subgroup 2- MD 1.2%,95% CI 1.06-1.37, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=8.25$, $I^2=52\%$, $p=0.08$,

Figure 8. Forrest plot showing comparison in terms of 24 hour urine protein

Fig 9. Forrest plot of 24 hour urine protein sub group 1 analysis

Figure 10. Funnel plot of the mean differences in 24 hour urine protein versus standard errors of the mean errors of all 5 studies assessing hyperuricemic effect on 24 hour urine protein in sub group 1

Figure 11. Forrest plot for subgroup 2 for analysis of 24 hour urine protein

Figure 12. Funnel plot of the mean differences in 24 hour urine protein versus standard errors of the mean errors of all 5 studies assessing hyperuricemic effect on 24 hour urine protein in sub group

3.5 Relationship between hyperuricemia and diastolic blood pressure

744 patients enrolled in a preliminary analysis of 5 studies revealed a significant increase in diastolic blood pressure in hyperuricemic IGAN patients [(MD 5.04% 95%CI: 3.87-6.21, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=103.13$, $I^2=96\%$, $p < 0.00001$) fig.13]. Fixed model analysis was used which did not alter the results. Like in other previous analyses, further analysis of a subgroup of 3 studies (441 patients), with similar characteristics and no heterogeneity, showed that there is a significant increase in diastolic pressure in hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 1.5% 95%CI: 0.08-2.93, $p=0.04$; heterogeneity $X^2=0.64$, $I^2=0\%$, $p=0.73$; fig 14). It is worth to note that sensitivity analysis demonstrated no changes from initial results. We considered this subgroup analysis to be our final results. (MD 1.5% 95%CI: 0.08-2.93, $p=0.04$; favours hyperuricemia).

Figure 13. Forrest plot showing comparison in terms of diastolic blood pressure.

Figure 14. Forrest plot in sub group analysis in terms of diastolic blood pressure

Figure 15. Funnel plot regarding diastolic blood pressure studies.

3.6 Relationship between hyperuricemia and systolic blood pressure

Significant increase in systolic blood pressure of hyperuricemic IGAN patients was proven in a meta-analysis of 4 studies of 651 patients [(MD 9.10% 95%CI: 7.44-10.77, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=163.93$, $I^2=98\%$, $p < 0.00001$) fig 16]. Taking into consideration of the dissimilarity among the studies and after excluding the study in which there was a higher mean difference in systolic blood pressure, a subgroup meta-analysis (3 studies, 541 patients) was carried out. This revealed that there was a clinically significant increase in systolic blood pressure in hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 3.55% 95%CI: 1.67-5.43, $p=0.0002$ heterogeneity $X^2=7.65$, $I^2=74\%$, $p=0.02$; fig 17). Unlikely, sensitivity analysis using a random model showed a non-significant increase in the systolic blood pressure in hyperuricemic patients in this sub group (; Tau^2 9.29, $X^2=7.65$, $I^2=74\%$ $p=0.02$, MD 3.40,

95%CI: -0.75-7.56 **p=0.11**; fig 18). In conclusion hyperuricemia may affect the severity of systolic blood pressure in IGAN patients.

Figure 16. Forrest plot of systolic blood pressure

Figure 17. Forrest plot in systolic blood pressure sub group analysis using fixed model effect.

Figure 18. Forrest plot analysis in systolic blood pressure sub group using random effect model.

Figure 19. Funnel plot in systolic blood pressure sub group

3.7 Relationship between hyperuricemia and different pathological features of IGAN

- a) Concerning initial analysis (4 studies, 1000 patients) about *mesangial proliferation* we found out a clinically significant increase in the degree of mesangial proliferation among hyperuricemic IGAN patients [(MD 0.12% 95%CI: 0.06-0.19, $p < 0.0003$; heterogeneity $X^2=7.81$, $I^2=62\%$, $p=0.05$) fig 20]. But I^2 being 62%, we decided to do a further subgroup analysis with 3 studies and involving 890 patients. We showed that the significant increase in degree of mesangial proliferation was maintained among hyperuricemic patients and the heterogeneity was $I^2=0\%$; (MD 0.09% 95%CI: 0.02-0.16, $p=0.01$; heterogeneity $X^2=0.93$, $I^2=0\%$, $p=0.63$; fig 21)

We regarded the sub group analysis to be final proposed result (MD 0.09% 95%CI: 0.02-0.16; favours hyperuricemia). Furthermore, sensitivity analysis did not bring about any changes.

- b) First meta-analysis of studies (4 studies, 1000 patients) involving *degree of glomerulosclerosis* revealed a clinically significant increase of glomerulosclerosis among hyperuricemic patients [(MD 0.37% 95%CI: 0.33-0.41, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=77.94$, $I^2=96\%$, $p < 0.00001$)

Fig 23]. Further sub group analysis of 3 studies (943 patients) maintained the clinically significant increase of glomerulosclerosis among hyperuricemia patients but with less heterogeneity (MD 0.31% 95%CI: 0.27-0.36, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=7.43$, $I^2=73\%$, $p=0.02$; fig 24). Sensitivity analysis revealed no alterations. Final result is MD 0.31% 95%CI: 0.27-0.36, $p < 0.00001$; favours hyperuricemia.

- c) In an analysis of 5 studies involving 550 patients there was a significant increase in level of *tubulointerstitial nephritis* among hyperuricemic IGAN patients [(MD 1.32% 95%CI: 1.28-1.36, $p < 0.003$; heterogeneity $X^2=15.88$, $I^2=75\%$, $p < 0.00001$) fig 26]. More meticulous analysis of 4 studies (493

patients) maintained the previous clinical significance but with less heterogeneity (MD 1.29% 95%CI: 1.25-1.34, $p < 0.00001$; heterogeneity $X^2=6.79$, $I^2=56\%$, $p=0.08$: fig 27). Sensitivity analysis showed no changes. Final result shows MD 1.29% 95%CI: 1.25-1.34, $p < 0.00001$: favours hyperuricemia.

Figure 20. Forrest plot of degree of mesangial proliferation

Figure 21. Forrest plot in terms of degree of mesangial proliferation subgroup.

Figure 22. Funnel plot of studies assessing the degree of mesangial proliferation

Figure 23. Forrest plot for glomerulosclerosis

Figure 24. Forrest plot of analysis of glomerulosclerosis subgroup

Figure 25. Funnel plot for glomerulosclerosis

Figure 26. Forrest plot for tubulointerstitial nephritis

Figure 27. Forrest plot for tubulointerstitial nephritis sub group.

Figure 28. Funnel plot for tubulointerstitial nephritis

4. Discussion

Uric acid is an end product of the metabolic breakdown of purine nucleotides in humans. The enzyme xanthine oxidase causes oxidation of xanthine and hypoxanthine to yield uric acid. The amount of uric acid in the body depends on the balance between the amount of purines eaten in food, the amount of uric acid synthesized within the body (e.g., through cell turnover), and the amount of uric acid that is excreted in urine or through the gastrointestinal tract. About 30% of uric acid is excreted in the intestinal tract; uric acid is secreted by intestinal mucosal cells into the lumen, then broken down to ammonia by the bacteria and finally excreted in the feces.

70% of uric acid is excreted by the kidney; urate is freely filtered at the glomerulus, reabsorbed, secreted, and then again reabsorbed in the proximal tubule.

The kidneys manage uric acid by filtration at the glomerulus, reabsorption, secretion, and finally post-secretory reabsorption.

Therefore, a changed uric acid excretion can result from decreased glomerular filtration, decreased tubular secretion, or enhanced tubular reabsorption.

In renal impairment, a decrease in the uric acid glomerular filtration accounts for the hyperuricemic state.

IGAN is a disease with a known antigen, galactose-deficient IgA1, which can show an antigen-antibody response leading to the formation of autoimmune complexes and their subsequent deposition in the mesangial area.

Some of the known poor prognostic factors of IGAN are heavy proteinuria, renal impairment at the time of diagnosis or renal biopsy, hypoalbuminemia, male gender, hypertension, age below 30 years ^[14, 20, and 21]

More recently hyperuricemia has gained much attention because of its possible role in aggravation of IGAN. It is speculated that IGAN patients with hyperuricemia have a worse prognosis compared to normouricemic patients.

Hyperuricemia also is believed to take part, directly or indirectly, in the pathogenesis of IGAN. Many studies have shown significant relationships between serum uric acid and tubular atrophy, interstitial fibrosis and inflammation, proteinuria and glomerulosclerosis ^[14, 15, and 16]. Other study did not show the direct influence of hyperuricemia on the pathological features of IGAN ^[17].

Based on that and to ascertain the real impact of hyperuricemia on the progression of IGAN, we carried out a meta-analysis and a systematic review.

a) Pathological characteristics.

We carried out analysis of pathological features of hyperuricemic IGAN patients based on Katafuchi score ^[22]. Katafuchi score is derived mostly from the pathological features based on Lee's classification of IGAN. Below is a detailed description of the above-mentioned classification.

It has five histological grades

I. Occasional slight mesangial thickening with or without hypercellularity. There are no tubular or interstitial changes.

II. <50% of glomeruli show localized mesangial proliferation and sclerosis. There are still no tubular and interstitial changes

III. Diffuse mesangial proliferation and thickening with focal and segmental variation. Occasional small crescents and adhesions can appear. Focal interstitial edema and infiltrates are occasionally present. Tubular atrophy is rare.

IV. Marked diffuse mesangial proliferation and sclerosis. Crescents are present in up to 45% of glomeruli. Tubular atrophy, interstitial inflammation, and occasional interstitial foam cells are present.

V. Similar to grade IV but crescents >45% and tubular interstitial changes are more severe.

Based on the above classification and following the peculiarities of Katafuchi score it can be deduced that a heavier degree of mesangial proliferation, the presence of crescent formation (and the extent of it), a more severe degree of glomerulosclerosis and tubulointerstitial nephritis correlate positively with the progression and prognosis of IGAN.

And finally, after carrying out our meta-analysis, we found that hyperuricemic IGAN patients were associated with worse pathological features: i.e. they had a more severe level of mesangial proliferation, more diffuse glomerulosclerosis and a higher degree of tubulointerstitial nephritis on biopsy compared to normouricemic ones. It means that hyperuricemia is a worse prognosis factor and can cause further progression of IGAN.

The mechanisms, involving uric acid, and leading to these definite pathological points are as follows: Uric acid causes

- 1) Endothelial dysfunction
- 2) Increased oxidative stress through xanthine oxidase (LDL oxidation and lipid peroxidation)

- 3) Vascular smooth muscle cells proliferation (COX-2, TXA-2, and PDGF)
- 4) Proinflammatory activity (MCP-1, IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α)

Endothelial dysfunction is mediated through impaired nitric oxide (NO) production and release by inhibiting the enzyme nitric oxide synthase. Nitric oxide is a vasodilator, and the presence of a high level of uric acid leads to an unopposed state of vasoconstriction, thus causing endothelial damage. Uric acid can also induce endothelial dysfunction by stimulating the release of alarmins (such as high mobility group box-1 protein) from endothelial cells. These alarmins activate Toll-like receptors^[23]

In an experiment, it was found that TNF- α released from the mesangium after IgA deposition activates renal tubular cells. The glomerulotubular interplay could have an important role in the pathogenesis of tubulointerstitial damage in IGAN^[24]

Renal progression matches more closely with the severity of tubulointerstitial lesions than with the degree of glomerular lesions in IGAN. Mesangial IgA deposition induces a local release of cytokines, complement, and angiotensin II leading to glomerular inflammation. It is ambiguous how mesangial IgA deposition leads to tubulointerstitial injury in IGAN. It has been hypothesized that mediators released from mesangial cells triggered by IgA deposition lead to activation of proximal tubular epithelial cells. In a study, it was found out that a glomerulotubular cross talk with mediators released from the mesangium contributes to the pathogenesis of tubulointerstitial damage in IGAN^[25] Kang and colleagues^[26], in their experimental study, found out that hyperuricaemic rats had more severe glomerular, vascular and interstitial changes than control. They also showed increased renin and COX-2 expression in blood vessels.

MCP-1/CCL2 is a 13 kDa chemokine of the CC chemokine group. CCL2 is shown to recruit monocytes into places of active inflammation^[27]. It has been demonstrated by Granata and others in 2006 that MCP-1 is related to nephropathy through p38 MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinases) phosphorylation. It is well speculated that uric acid mediates proinflammatory activity through induction of monocyte chemoattractant protein-1 and the MAPK pathway^[26]. This hypothesis was demonstrated in a few studies^[28]

Kanellis et al. showed that soluble uric acid stimulates the production of MCP-1 by rat vascular smooth cell muscles in vitro. It also showed the activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinases 44/42 (ERK 44/42) MAPK and that this process would ultimately mediate uric acid – induced increase in MCP-1 synthesis. In the same study, they have also found out that the inhibition of p38 MAPK pathway partially blocked the increase in MCP-1 (which in a way confirms the relationship between MAPK pathway and MCP-1). This uric acid – induced MCP-1 synthesis was also shown to be mediated by COX-2^[28].

This concept of uric acid- induced MCP-1 synthesis was also proven by Cirrillo et al. they also demonstrated that uric acid most probably induced MCP-1 expression in human proximal tubular epithelial cells^[31]. Cirrillo et al. examined the effect of hyperuricemia in rats with remnant kidneys and found out that these rats have significantly worse renal function and glomerulosclerosis, and this was linked with a further increase of intrarenal inflammation^[31]. More interestingly, in a retrospective study, it was shown that allopurinol (a xanthine oxidase inhibitor) prevented an increase in serum level of MCP-1 in rats^[26]. It's also speculated that uric acid mediates inflammatory reactions through the induction of leucocyte adhesion proteins (ICAM -1) and MCP-1 that act together with oxidative stress and endothelial dysfunction to quicken the renal lesion^[29].

In some experimental studies, hyperuricemia and hyperuricosuria have been induced by uric acid and oxonic acid diet. The most significant light-microscopic findings were interstitial mononuclear infiltrations and fibrosis and tubular changes while glomeruli and blood vessels were normal in morphology^[30].

In another study^[31], the serum uric acid concentration correlated most strongly with chronic tubulointerstitial changes and less strongly with glomerulosclerosis. The serum level of uric acid also correlated with inflammatory cell infiltration both in glomeruli and interstitium. There were associations between serum uric acid and tubular atrophy and interstitial fibrosis. It seems possible that hyperuricemia acid may independently cause progression in IGAN by damaging tubulointerstitial tissue. Because of the central role of tubulointerstitial injury in the progression of IGAN, the significance of hyperuricemia may be quite important.

It has also been shown that renal interstitial fibrosis is induced by intrarenal deposition of uric acid crystals^[32, 33].

Mesangial cells undergo proliferation and matrix synthesis, causing an increase in the number of matrix cell number and accumulation of matrix. Many related factors, such as cytokines, growth mediators, matrix components, and interactions with other cells control the matrix cells^[34, 35].

Zhuang et al.^[36] showed uric acid mediates mesangial cell proliferation by NADPH/Reactive oxygen species (ROS)/ ERK1/2 pathways.

In 2013, Shen Shi Zhong analyzed 110 IGAN patients (out of which 55 were hyperuricemic), and he found out that the hyperuricemic ones had a more severe degree of mesangial proliferation, glomerulosclerosis and tubulointerstitial nephritis^[2]. Analysis of renal biopsies of 171 IGAN patients with elevated level serum uric acid by Gao Xue Yan^[5] in the same year, revealed a higher grade of glomerulosclerosis and mesangial proliferation. Reports following an analysis of two sets of patients, with low eGFR and normal eGFR, in Gen Yang Cheng's study, show the similar results as previously found by other authors^[11]. Liu Cui analyzed two groups of 26 hyperuricemic IGAN patients (with normal renal function and renal dysfunction) and showed that they have a higher degree of tubulointerstitial nephritis^[4].

Likewise, our meta-analysis of several studies confirmed that hyperuricemic IGAN patients have advanced pathological features on renal biopsy and are subsequently associated with worse prognosis and progression of the disease.

b) Urine protein level

The 24-hour urine protein is a distinct marker of kidney injury. It is known to everyone that the larger the quantity of protein in the urine the more severe the kidney damage is. There are several studies which have analyzed the relationship between hyperuricemia and the extent 24-hour proteinuria in IGAN patients.

149 IGAN patients with an increased level of serum uric acid show a higher grade proteinuria, a study by Tian Yun^[1]. Lian Xi Yan et al^[10] examined 39 IGAN patients whose

serum uric acid level was higher than other 87 IGAN ones, and they compared the degree of urine protein excretion in those patients. They found out that hyperuricemic patients were associated with a higher grade proteinuria. Cui and colleagues carried out a study on 148 patients with IGAN from January 2007 to December 2010 to observe the relationship between the level of serum uric acid and the clinical and pathological features of IGAN. They found that the level of serum uric acid had correlated with 24-hour proteinuria amount, blood pressure and kidney function in IGAN^[7]. They also found that tubulointerstitial lesions grade and morphologic lesions of renal artery were severe in the hyperuricemic group^[37]. Su Ji Kim et al^[8], from Korea, also demonstrated that hyperuricemic patients have more proteinuria than normouricemic patients.

Similarly, in our meta-analysis report, reports we concluded that hyperuricemia is associated with heavier proteinuria in IGAN patients and hence has a poorer prognosis.

Cheng et al. found out that among patients with hyperuricemia the prevalence of glomerular sclerosis, vasculopathy, and tubulointerstitial fibrosis were more significant compared to with normouricemic subjects^[11].

They hence concluded that serum uric acid level in IGAN patients affects the pathophysiology and prognosis of the IGAN.

Moreover, in their experiments they observed that increased serum uric acid causes kidney vasoconstriction and activation of the renin-angiotensin system^[11].

Kovács and associates, while investigating on IGAN patients with metabolic syndrome (at the time of diagnosis or during follow-up) found out that hyperuricemia is an independent risk factor for progression of IGAN^[37].

In a meta-analysis, it was revealed that higher albuminuria is a risk factor for kidney disease progression^[38]. It's accepted that a more extensive renal correlates positively with the higher extent of proteinuria.

Apart from the mechanisms mentioned above, there are also several other pathways by which uric acid can cause kidney damage.

Uric acid induces vascular smooth cell proliferation through different mediators, namely, cyclooxygenase -2, thromboxane A2 and platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF).

PDGF are known to contribute to renal fibrosis. PDGF causes kidney development by recruiting mesenchymal cells to the glomerular and tubulointerstitial parts. They furthermore control many processes including cell proliferation, cell migration, expression and accumulation of extracellular matrix, production and secretion of pro- and anti-inflammatory mediators, vascular permeability, and hemodynamics. Fibrotic kidneys are characterized by glomerulosclerosis, tubular atrophy, and dilatation, tubulointerstitial fibrosis^[39].

Activated mesangial cells produce cytokines including IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α , MCP-1, TGF- β , and PDGF. In an experimental study, it was found out that that these humoral mediators from mesangial cells first activate the podocytes before going to the tubulointerstitium either by glomerular filtration or by transportation via the postglomerular capillaries. After reaching the tubular compartment, these factors could stimulate tubular epithelial cells to produce other pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines that subsequently lead to tubular damage, interstitial mononuclear cells infiltration and fibrosis. The severity of tubulointerstitial damage in IGAN relates closely with the deteriorating renal function and the long-standing clinical outcome^[40].

Podocyte injury, of various causes, contributes largely to the severity of proteinuria. Indirectly, uric acid has been shown to cause podocyte impairment and hence adds up to the amount of urine protein excretion.

In an experimental study, to elucidate the mechanism of renal injury due to NOD-like receptor 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome, Hu et al. found out that fructose-induced hyperuricemia and dyslipidemia cause renal NLRP3 inflammasome activation. This activation was described by an increased expression of the NLRP3, apoptosis-associated speck-like protein (ASC) and caspase-1, causing an overproduction of interleukin (IL)-1 β and IL-18, as well as IL-6 and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) in rats. The elevated levels of these pro-inflammatory cytokines led to an impairment in the renal Janus-activated kinase 2 (JAK2)/signal transducer and activator of transcription 3 (STAT3)/peroxisome

proliferator-activated receptor α (PAPR- α), and insulin receptor (IR)/insulin receptor substrate 1 (IRS1)/protein kinase B (Akt)/extracellular signal-regulated kinase1/2 (ERK1/2) signaling pathways with over-expression of suppressor of cytokine signaling 3 (SOCS3), worsening renal lipid accumulation and injury in fructose-fed rats. Use of allopurinol, a xanthine oxidase inhibitor, blocked the NLRP3 inflammasome activation to improve the signaling impairments and decrease lipid accumulation in the kidney of rats. These results suggest that the activation of renal NLRP3 inflammasome may have a significant role in the relation between renal inflammation, JAK2/STAT3/PAPR- α and IR/IRS1/Akt/ERK1/2 signaling impairment, and lipid accumulation caused by fructose^[41].

In another experiment, Wand and colleagues^[42] focused on fructose-induced hyperuricemia causing glomerular and podocyte injury through oxidative stress. In this study, they concentrated on microRNA-377 (miR-377) as being a marker of oxidative stress in renal cortex of fructose-fed rats. And this was believed to be positively correlated with podocyte injury and albuminuria in metabolic syndrome. The high fructose diet has caused an elevated miR-377 expression, decreased superoxide dismutase (SOD) expression and activity, and caused O₂ (-) and H₂O₂ overproduction in kidney cortex or glomeruli of rats. These reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation amplified p38 MAPK phosphorylation and thioredoxin-interacting protein (TXNIP) expression and stimulated the NOD-like receptor pyrin domain-containing 3 (NLRP3) inflammasome to produce interleukin-1 β in kidney glomeruli of fructose-fed rats.

Allopurinol was found to ameliorate fructose-induced hyperuricemia, podocyte injury, and albuminuria in these rats.

c) Blood pressure

It is universally known that high blood pressure can be the result of a renal dysfunction, or hypertension can cause more kidney damage. Hyperuricemia also predicts the development of high blood pressure and an independent relationship between uric acid levels and the incidence has already been previously reported^[43].

Bakan Ali and colleagues, from Turkey, analyzed a set IGAN patients with hyper and normouricemia and compared their level of blood pressure. They found out that systolic

and diastolic blood pressures were significantly higher among hyperuricemics^[9]. A study from Korea by Su Ji Kim and colleagues also showed a higher degree of systolic and diastolic blood pressure among hyperuricemic IGAN patients^[8]. In their respective analyses, Chinese authors^[2, 11] also revealed the same results as their other Asian colleagues.

With regards to the relationship between blood pressure and kidney disease, we have looked for a few relevant studies.

In a study done by Agarwal, it was shown that in older patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), systolic blood pressure forecasts end-stage renal disease (ESRD) and a greater systolic blood pressure (SBP) and lower diastolic blood pressure (DBP) predicts all-cause mortality. Lower blood pressure of <110/70 mmHg is an indicator of higher mortality in older individuals with advanced CKD^[44]. Chiang et al.^[45] in Taiwan showed that diabetic patients with chronic kidney disease have a J-shaped relationship between systolic blood pressure and cardiovascular or renal outcomes, whereas nondiabetic CKD patients do not. Klag et al. proved that the relative risk of end-stage kidney failure was >20-fold higher for patients with stage 4 hypertension (SBP> 210 mmHg or DBP > 120 mmHg) than for patients with optimal blood pressure levels (SBP > 120 mmHg and DBP > 80 mmHg)^[46]. This result once again points towards the J relationship between systolic blood pressure and renal outcomes mentioned above. Rifkin et al. showed that when systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure are both considered separately, they have a U- shaped relationship with mortality in chronic kidney disease patients^[47]. This U-shaped relationship was proven in the study done by Mitka where a low systolic and diastolic and a high systolic and diastolic blood pressure were both associated with increased mortality risks in chronic kidney disease patients^[48].

Based on several studies, we carry out a meta-analysis that has given us with interesting results. We found out that hyperuricemia is associated with a more elevated diastolic and systolic blood pressure in IGAN patients.

But it cannot be unquestionably concluded that hyperuricemic IGAN patients are associated with higher systolic blood pressure compared to normouricemic ones. In our meta-analysis,

we revealed that there was a clinically significant increase in systolic blood pressure in hyperuricemic IGAN patients (MD 3.55% 95%CI: 1.67-5.43, **p=0.0002** heterogeneity $X^2=7.65$, $I^2=74\%$, $p=0.02$; fig 8.2). Unlikely, the sensitivity analysis using a random model showed a non-clinically significant increase in the systolic blood pressure in hyperuricemic patients in this subgroup (; Tau^2 9.29, $X^2=7.65$, $I^2=74\%$ $p=0.02$, MD 3.40, 95%CI: -0.75-7.56 **p=0.11**; fig 8.3). In conclusion, we suggest that hyperuricemia **may** affect the severity of systolic blood pressure in IGAN patients. But this association is not definitive. We suggest that further studies should be carried out, with more patients, to elucidate and confirm this association.

Will the effect of lowering uric acid in IGAN patients be of more benefit to diastolic or systolic blood pressures? The answers to these questions can only be answered after careful, adequately powered randomized control trials (concerning these themes) be performed.

In a few studies, treatment of hyperuricemia with allopurinol (xanthine oxidase inhibitor) has shown some benefit in hypertension control and hence subsequently (indirectly) delaying the progression of IGAN.

Shi et al. carried out a study on 353 IGAN patients to try to find out an association of serum uric acid and the progression of kidney disease over a mean period of 5 years ^[17]. 40 hyperuricemic IGAN patients randomly received allopurinol (100 mg/d to 300 mg/d) or usual therapy for 6 months. The end-points were kidney disease progression or blood pressure rising. In their trial, allopurinol did not significantly change kidney progression or proteinuria. Nevertheless, they found that the dose of the antihypertensive drug was decreased in 7 of 9 cases within the allopurinol group compared to none of 9 cases in the control group.

In an experimental study ^[49], hyperuricemia causes arteriopathy of preglomerular vessels, which impairs the autoregulatory response of afferent arterioles, resulting in glomerular hypertension. Luminal dysfunction caused by vascular wall thickening produces severe renal hypoperfusion. The resulting ischemia is a potent stimulus that induces

tubulointerstitial inflammation and fibrosis, as well as arterial hypertension. This is a potential mechanism by which hyperuricemia may lead to hypertension and renal disease.

In another interventional study, Feriozzi S et al. found out that angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor therapy was linked with a lower diastolic blood pressure and a slowing of the rate of decline in renal function, but no change in proteinuria in IGAN^[50].

Hyperuricemia may reflect a decline in renal blood flow and early hypertensive nephrosclerosis. A decreased renal blood flow could change the balance between medullary and cortical circulation, possibly resulting in a reduction in urate secretion. It can in return lead to an increase in the serum uric acid level^[13] and thus creates a vicious circle. Hypertension can also lead to microvascular disease that can cause local tissue ischemia^[51] Tissue ischemia can then lead to an elevation of synthesis of uric acid and thus resulting in a more severe increase in serum uric acid. These mechanisms might suggest that serum uric acid level might be a consequence rather than a cause of hypertension.

Serum uric acid may have a pathologic role in renal vasoconstriction, endothelial dysfunction, inflammatory response, oxidative stress^[52]. The mechanisms involved are endothelial dysfunction, by inhibiting nitric oxide synthetase, activating the renin-angiotensin system and causing proinflammation^[53].

Studies have demonstrated that activation of the renin-angiotensin system is due to several mechanisms such as declining nitric oxide synthase in the juxtaglomerular apparatus or by decreasing kidney perfusion by stimulating the afferent arteriolar vascular smooth cell proliferation and through the induction of COX-2 in the macula densa and arterioles^[54-58].

In a study by Konishi et al. it was found that the impairment of NO synthesis and a reduced reaction of the renin-angiotensin system are attributable to the changed sodium sensitivity of blood pressure in patients with immunoglobulin A glomerulonephritis^[59].

Chronic kidney disease patients are associated with increased vascular calcification. Vascular calcification is associated with decreased large arterial compliance and hence compromised baroreflex sensitivity resulting in amplified blood pressure variability and troubled blood pressure regulation^[60].

d) Nitrogenous waste products

Blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine are end products of nitrogen metabolism. They are mostly excreted by the kidney. Due to a higher degree of mesangial proliferation, a more severe glomerulosclerosis, enhanced tubulointerstitial nephritis, increased level of protein excretion (and hence more risk for proinflammatory reactions at the tubular level), and a greater range of systolic and diastolic blood pressure among hyperuricemic patients, it can be concluded that uric acid ultimately causes and might be associated with more severe renal dysfunction. The glomerular filtration rate (GFR) is decreased and hence causing accumulation of nitrogenous waste products.

To an individual level, the increase in blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine is positively correlated to the degree of renal injury. Following our meticulous meta-analysis, we have found out that hyperuricemia is strongly associated with a higher level of those blood urea nitrogen and serum creatinine in IGAN patients.

This meta-analysis has got a few limitations. It includes only published data. This analysis was also limited by the methodological quality of the studies included. The second limitation is that there was heterogeneity. There was heterogeneity in the source populations, and sample sizes. Meta-analyses of different subgroups, in which dissimilar studies were excluded, partly effaced the disadvantage of heterogeneity.

Finally, following a thorough examination of several studies and after carrying out this delicate meta-analysis and systematic review, we conclude that hyperuricemia is a critical risk factor for progression of IGAN. Nevertheless, we recommend that adequately powered, high-quality randomized control trials be carried out to evaluate the benefits and risks of urate-lowering therapy on progression of IGAN.

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Literature review

HYPERURICEMIA AND ITS CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE IN THE PROGRESSION OF KIDNEY DISEASE

Introduction

The effect of uric acid on the initiation and progression of kidney diseases has been extensively debated lately. But this relationship still seems very ambiguous.

This literature review will bring about the different mechanism pathways in which uric acid is shown to directly or indirectly influence the progression of renal diseases.

The different experimental and clinical studies are also discussed; in a way to support the mechanisms and the various hypotheses of uric acid being a risk factor for chronic kidney disease progression.

Uric acid metabolism pathway

Uric acid is a product of purine nucleotides breakdown in humans. The enzymes xanthine oxidase causes oxidation of xanthine and hypoxanthine to yield uric acid.

There are two sources of uric acid are endogenous, being 80% of the uric acid found in our body (after nucleic acid catabolism) and exogenous, obtained from food rich in purines and nucleic acid

The quantity of uric acid in the body depends on the balance between the amount of purines eaten in food, the amount of urate synthesized in the body (e.g., through cell turnover), and the amount of uric acid that is excreted in urine or through the gastrointestinal tract.

To achieve homeostasis, the rate of uric acid absorption and excretion are balanced out at 700mg/day. About 30% of uric acid is excreted in the intestinal tract; uric acid is secreted by intestinal mucosal cells into the lumen, then broken down to ammonia by the bacteria and finally excreted in the feces.

70% of uric acid is excreted by the kidney; Urate is freely filtered at the glomerulus, reabsorbed, secreted, and then again reabsorbed in the proximal tubule.

A urate/anion exchanger (URAT1) has been identified in the brush-border membrane of the kidneys. A human organic anion transporter (hOAT1) has also been found.

Another urate transporter (UAT) has been found to facilitate urate efflux out of the cells. These transporters may account for the reabsorption, secretion, and reabsorption pattern of renal handling of urate.

Figure 1: Mechanism of uric acid formation

Figure 2: Metabolic pathway of uric acid

Pathogenesis of hyperuricemia

The serum concentration of uric acid is at 6.4-6.8 mg/dL (conversion unit of uric acid: 1mg/dL=59.48 μ mol/l) at ambient conditions, with the upper limit of solubility placed at 7 mg/dL.

Hyperuricemia can occur because of decreased excretion (**underexcretors**), increased production (**overproducers**), and a combination of these two mechanisms.

The most causes of hyperuricemia are among underexcretors. The kidneys manage uric acid by filtration at the glomerulus, reabsorption, secretion, and, finally, post-secretory reabsorption.

Therefore, a changed uric acid excretion can result from decreased glomerular filtration, decreased tubular secretion, or enhanced tubular reabsorption. In renal impairment, a decline in the uric acid glomerular filtration accounts for the hyperuricemic state.

Decreased tubular secretion of uric acid occurs in patients with acidosis (e.g., diabetic ketoacidosis, ethanol or salicylate intoxication, starvation ketosis).^[1]The organic acids that accumulate in these conditions compete with uric acid for tubular secretion. Eventually, enhanced reabsorption of uric acid distal to the site of secretion is the mechanism believed to be responsible for the hyperuricemia seen with diuretic therapy and diabetes insipidus.

Overproduction accounts for only a small number of patients presenting with hyperuricemia. The reasons for hyperuricemia in overproducers may be either exogenous (a diet rich in purines) or endogenous (increased purine nucleotide breakdown). A small percentage of overproducers have enzymatic defects that account for their hyperuricemia. Augmented purine degradation can result from rapid cell proliferation and turnover (blast crisis of leukemia) or cell death (rhabdomyolysis, cytotoxic therapy).

Causes of hyperuricemia that are of the mixed type have a dual action, both increasing production and decreasing excretion of uric acid.^[2]High intake of alcohol (ethanol), an important cause of hyperuricemia, has a dual action that is explained by multiple mechanisms. Ethanol increases production of uric acid by increasing production of lactic acid, hence lactic acidosis. As an end-product of its fermentation process, beer additionally contributes to increasing purine concentration. Ethanol decreases excretion of uric acid by promoting dehydration.^[3]

Risk Factors for chronic kidney diseases

A *risk factor* is a factor that has an association with a disease or disease process; the presence of the variable in an individual or a population is associated with an increased risk

of the presence or future development of the disease. Thus, risk factors may be useful for identifying subjects at increased risk for a disease or for a particular outcome that results from a disease process.

Susceptibility risk factors are associated with an individual's increased risk of developing CKD after exposure to a factor that has the potential to cause renal damage.

Initiation factors directly cause or initiate kidney damage in a susceptible individual. Examples include exposure to nephrotoxic drugs, urinary tract obstruction, or primary glomerulopathies that may provoke CKD in some but not necessarily all exposed individuals.

Progression factors contribute to the progression of kidney damage once CKD has developed. An example is hypertension, which exacerbates raised intraglomerular hydraulic pressure and, therefore, accelerates the glomerular damage.

The different progression factors for chronic kidney disease (CKD) are

1. ethnicity
2. low nephron number
3. diabetes mellitus (DM)
4. hypertension (HBP)
5. obesity
6. high protein intake

7. pregnancy
8. acute kidney injury (AKI)
9. cardiovascular disease (CVD)
10. albuminuria
11. hypoalbuminemia
12. anemia
13. dyslipidemia
- 14. hyperuricemia**
- 15. asymmetric dimethyl arginine (ADMA)**
- 16. hyperphosphatemia**
- 17. smoking**
- 18. Nephrotoxins.**

The main issue of this review is to discuss how hyperuricemia influences the progression of CKD. Arbitrarily hyperuricemia is considered when the serum uric acid is ≥ 7.0 mg/dl in men and ≥ 6.5 mg/dl in women.

History

Hyperuricemia is quite common in kidney disease due to decreased uric acid clearance. It was first thought of being a marker of kidney damage and only secondarily an independent risk factor for kidney disease development and progression.

Recent studies have raised the possibility that uric acid may have a causal role in cardiovascular and renal diseases. ^[4] Garrod, in the early 1800s, found out that increased serum uric acid causes gout. Thereafter hyperuricemia was proposed to have a causal role in a variety of cardiovascular and renal conditions, including hypertension, arteriosclerosis, kidney, and heart diseases. ^[4]

A relationship between elevated serum uric acid with HBP, cardiovascular, renal and metabolic disease has been reported throughout the 20th century in gout patients in the 1870's. ^[5] In 1909, Henri Huchard noted that renal arteriosclerosis (the pathologic lesion of hypertension) was present in patients with hyperuricemia and suggested, for the first time, a potential association between uric acid and kidney damage. ^[6] In 1928, Gudzent described the relationship between gouty arthritis and renal disease. The histopathological

lesion, ‘gouty nephropathy’, was found in autopsies of 79–99% of patients with gout.^[7] Interstitial fibrosis, glomerulosclerosis and renal arteriosclerosis and arterial wall thickening caused by intimal fibrosis were found in biopsies. Klinenberg and colleagues in 1975 studied a group of asymptomatic hyperuricaemic patients and found that they had a disproportionately high prevalence of renal dysfunction compared with healthy persons with no hyperuricaemia^[8] Moreover, many patients with gout also had comorbidities such as hypertension and vascular disease, and hence some professionals thought that the renal injury in gout was secondary to these latter diseases rather than to uric acid per se^[9]. Rather bizarrely, gout was no more considered as a cause of CKD, and the association of hyperuricemia with CKD was only attributed to the retention of serum uric acid that occurs as the glomerular filtration rate declines. In the late 1990s, some specialists reevaluated the significance of uric acid in cardiovascular and renal diseases.^[10] It was thought that the mechanism by which uric acid would cause kidney dysfunction would be through crystals deposition in the kidney, similar to the way it causes gout. But when laboratory animals with CKD were made hyperuricemic, the renal dysfunction progressed very quickly in spite of an absence of crystals in the kidney^[11] Recent epidemiological, experimental, and clinical studies have consistently raised the possibility that uric acid may have a causative role in the onset and progression of hypertension, cardiovascular disease, and renal disease.

Causes of hyperuricemia

1. Drugs: Diuretics, salicylates, pyrazinamide, cyclosporine, nicotinic acid
2. Diet
3. High dietary fructose intake
4. Ketogenic diet
5. Starvation
6. Reduced excretion due to chronic kidney disease
7. Malignancies, polycythemia vera, hemolytic anemias and other conditions with a rapid cellular turnover
8. Genetic causes: Mutations in enzymes involved in purine metabolism, such as xanthine oxidase, urate transporter/channel, organic anion transporters 1 and 3 and urate transporter 1, UMOD associated renal diseases, phosphofructokinase deficiency

Major pathophysiological mechanisms of uric acid induced damage

1. Endothelial dysfunction through impaired NO production and release
2. Increased oxidative stress mainly through xanthine oxidase (LDL oxidation and lipid peroxidation)
3. Platelet activation (platelet aggregation and thrombosis)
4. Vascular smooth muscle cells proliferation (COX-2, TXA2, and PDGF)
5. Proinflammatory activity (MCP-1, IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α)

Note: NO, nitric oxide; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; COX-2, cyclooxygenase-2; TXA2, thromboxane A2; PDGF, platelet-derived growth factor; MCP-1, monocyte chemoattractant factor-1; IL, interleukin; TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor- α .

The changes brought to our body by hyperuricemia

Uric acid is the end product of purine metabolism in humans. Most mammals possess the enzyme uricase that converts uric acid into allantoin which is excreted in the urine. But humans and greater apes don't have this enzyme or are thought to have a mutated form which has been rendered futile. Therefore uric acid thus remains the end product of the catabolic pathway.

1. In the extra cellular space, uric acid has anti-oxidant activity. Urate, the soluble form of uric acid in the blood, reacts with various oxidants such as hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radicals, and nitric oxide derivatives and neutralizes their effects.^[12] Superoxide dismutase is an enzyme with important activity in the vascular endothelium. Uric acid is thought to inhibit the degradation and deactivation of this enzyme. Reactive oxygen species is thought to be related to local inflammation, impairment in nitric oxide generation, an activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), insulin resistance and fat accumulation. Peroxynitrite-induced protein nitrosylation, lipid, and protein peroxidation are all prevented by uric acid and thus, resulting in getting rid of free radicals and chelating transitional

- metal ions. However, many animal and human studies show uric acid as a pro-oxidant.
2. But once it enters into the cells, uric acid has pro-oxidant effects; where it can induce NADPH oxidase with the induction of mitochondrial dysfunction.^[13]
 3. It is being postulated that uric acid enters the vascular endothelium through specific organic anion transporters namely the URATE1. This is urate- anion exchanger that is specific to the renal tubular epithelium. However, the presence of this molecule in the vascular endothelium most probably explains the intracellular effects of urate^[14] Intracellularly, uric acid activates protein kinases (p38 and Erk1/2) and nuclear transcription factors [nuclear factor kappa B (NK-kB) and activator protein -1 (AP-1)] leading to proliferation and proinflammation.
 4. As a result, vascular smooth muscle cells produce growth factors (platelet-derived growth factor), vasoconstrictive substances (angiotensin II, thromboxane A₂),cytokines, proinflammatory molecules [C- reactive protein (CRP) and monocyte chemoattractant protein- 1 (MCP-1)].^[11]
 5. Uric acid is believed to upregulate the expression of type 1 angiotensin II receptors in endothelial cells and vascular smooth muscles cells.^[15]
 6. Hyperuricemia stimulates the production of interleukin 1 β , interleukin -6 and tumor necrosis factor- α ; all of which are proinflammatory substances.
 7. Moreover uric acid inhibits the nitric oxide synthase enzyme and thus lowering the production of nitric oxide, ultimately contributing to endothelial dysfunction. Uric acid can also induce endothelial dysfunction by stimulating the release of alarmins (such as high mobility group box-1 protein) from endothelial cells. These alarmins activate Toll- like receptor pathways.^[16]
 8. In addition, uric acid seems to cause platelet adhesion and aggregation, thus contributing to vascular thrombosis.^[17]

Figure 3. Non-renal and renal effects of uric acid

Figure 4. Pathways by which uric acid induces proliferation and inflammation mechanisms.

Uric acid enters vascular smooth muscle cells through specific OAT and activates intracellular MAP kinases, p38 and Erk 1/2, and nuclear transcription factors (NF- κ B and AP-1), leading these cells to achieve a proliferative and inflammatory character.

OAT, organic anion transporter; MAP, mitogen-activated protein; NF- κ B, nuclear factor kappa B; AP-1, activator protein-1; COX-2, cyclooxygenase-2; TXA₂, thromboxane; PDGF, platelet-derived growth factor; MCP-1, monocyte chemoattractant protein-1.

Epidemiology

Serum uric acid is eliminated mainly by the kidneys, and the compensatory increased excretion by the bowel in case of renal impairment, is not sufficiently effective. Thus, serum uric acid increases as the GFR falls, with approximately half of the patients becoming hyperuricemic by the time dialysis is initiated. ^[18]

Experimental studies suggest that uric acid may lead to kidney disease mainly by causing systemic and glomerular hypertension, but in renal disease this mechanism may become less significant as systemic hypertension commonly results as a consequence of sodium and water retention. Some studies have found that hyperuricemia can predict progression in patients already having CKD, especially in diabetes and IgA nephropathy.^[19]

In subjects with normal renal function, an increased serum uric acid has been found to independently predict the development of CKD, including ESRD. An elevated serum uric acid has also been found to independently predict the development of CKD in subjects with IgA nephropathy^[20-22] and of graft failure in transplant patients with chronic allograft nephropathy.^[23] In diabetes, serum uric acid is often low due to the effects of glycosuria in increasing urate excretion. Poor glucose control is often associated with low serum uric acid level.^[24]

Good diabetes control being associated with renoprotection, it is predictable that elevated uric acid levels would be linked with better renal outcomes. But in patients having DM I, an elevated serum uric acid, even when within the normal range, is a strong predictor for the development of both microalbuminuric and albuminuric diabetic kidney disease, and also predicts the development of CKD.^[25-27] Uric acid also predicts the development and progression of CKD in subjects with DM II.^[27]

Hence, an elevated uric acid is linked to the development of CKD, but not always with the progression of CKD. Moreover, hyperuricemia has been associated with both the presence of intrarenal arteriolar lesions^[22, 29] and with an increased risk of cardiovascular mortality in subjects with CKD.^[30,31] However, once patients reach end-stage renal disease, there is a reverse J-curve, in which both high and lower uric acid levels convey increased cardiovascular risk and mortality^[32].

Experimental studies

In a rat animal model hyperuricemia was induced by the administration of the uricase inhibitor oxonic acid, and a renal vascular disease including cortical vasoconstriction, afferent arteriolar swelling, and glomerular hypertension has been found. These were partially reversible by the administration of the Xanthine Oxidase inhibitor febuxostat.^[33]

Some mechanisms have been proposed for explaining these endothelial abnormalities induced by elevated serum uric acid. Incubation of vascular smooth muscle cells with uric acid has been found to stimulate proliferation, angiotensin II production, and oxidative stress which was reversed by the addition of captopril or losartan, suggesting an effect mediated through the renin-angiotensin system.^[34] Hemodynamic changes found in the hyperuricemic rat model were reversed by the addition of a superoxide scavenger, thus supporting the link between elevated urate levels and damage induced by reactive-oxygen species (oxidative stress).^[33] Expression of endothelin-1^[35] which has been consistently associated with cardiovascular disease has also been postulated as a potential mechanism of an association between hyperuricemia and cardiovascular conditions. Endothelin-1 has vasoconstrictive effect by binding to the receptors ET-A and ET-B in human vascular cells^[36]. Urate, known as an extracellular molecule, enters vascular endothelial cells most probably by the renal afferent arterioles expressed URAT1^[34]. Previously thought to be found only in renal tubular cells, the presence of URAT1 in endothelial cells may explain the intracellular effects of urate. Pathologically, light microscopy (PAS staining) of the kidney in hyperuricemic rats shows minor, non-specific, changes consisting of tubular dilatation and atrophy in the renal cortex^[32] and some glomerular sclerosis. Thickening of the afferent arterioles and some interlobular arteries, with sparing of the larger vessels, can also be seen. In humans, chronic hyperuricemia is also characterized by crystal-independent renal damage. The lesion gouty nephropathy consists of interstitial fibrosis, glomerulosclerosis and renal arteriosclerosis and arterial wall thickening, caused by intimal fibrosis, which resembles the lesion observed in hyperuricemic rats. (Found by Gudzent in 1928).^[35]

Clinical studies

The best way to check the involvement of uric acid in the pathogenesis of CKD progression is to use uric acid lowering drugs and show its effectiveness in slowing the rate of renal disease progression. There are a few clinical studies and these too, with limitations.

Studies in which cessation of allopurinol leads to further deterioration in kidney disease do bring indirect evidence of the clinical significance of uric acid in the progression of

CKD.^[37,38] Allopurinol, by inhibiting xanthine oxidase, exerts antioxidant activity along with reducing serum uric acid levels. Xanthine oxidase is a superoxide-producing enzyme, and its activity can be inhibited completely by the use of allopurinol. Experimentally, allopurinol happens to prevent vascular complications through its antioxidant effects by blocking the generation of free radicals.^[39] But a randomized study has failed to demonstrate this effect of allopurinol compared with placebo in reducing lipid peroxidation and total oxidative stress in patients with diabetes.^[40] Moreover, allopurinol has been found to improve endothelial function in diabetics, smokers, hypercholesterolemic patients, and those with congestive heart failure.^[41]

LIFE (Losartan Intervention for Endpoint Reduction) Study was designed to compare losartan and atenolol regarding cardiovascular morbidity and mortality, and not to investigate the role of uric acid reduction in cardiovascular events. However the analysis of data showed that the hypouricemic effect of losartan appeared to explain a significant 29% of the favorable treatment effect on the primary composite endpoint (myocardial infarction, stroke, death).^[42] Moreover, the association between uric acid lowering by losartan and renal endpoints, defined as doubling of serum creatinine or ESRD, was determined in a recent analysis of patients with type II diabetes and nephropathy participating in the Reduction of Endpoints in Non-Insulin-Dependent Diabetes Mellitus with the Angiotensin II Antagonist Losartan^[43]

The risk of renal events was decreased by 6% per 0.5 mg/dL decrease in serum uric acid during the first 6 months of the study. This effect had no connection with other risk markers, including eGFR and albuminuria.

By Siu et al. the direct clinical significance of hypouricemic treatment in kidney disease progression was investigated in a randomized study where a group of patients with hyperuricemia and CKD were treated with allopurinol or continued their usual therapy for 12 months.^[39] Study endpoints were an elevation in serum creatinine greater than 40% of baseline values or ESRD and initiation of dialysis therapy. In the treatment group, only 16% of the patients reached endpoints during 12 months of follow-up as compared with 46% patients in the control. There were no statistically significant differences in systolic or diastolic BP between the two groups at the end of the study. There was also no statistical significance to a lower serum creatinine in the treatment group compared with controls

after 12 months of therapy. This study had several limitations that prevent generalization of the results, such as small sample size, short duration of treatment, and the Asian origin of patients.

Moreover, during the study, patients continued to take antihypertensive drugs with possible renoprotective properties. Similarly, Goicoechea et al. studied patients with eGFR <60 mL/min who were randomly assigned to treatment with allopurinol or to continue the usual therapy and concluded after 24 months that allopurinol reduces the progression of renal disease and cardiovascular risk.^[44] Specifically, serum uric acid and CRP levels were significantly decreased in subjects treated with allopurinol and eGFR increased compared with a significant decrease in controls. Allopurinol treatment slowed down renal disease progression independently of age, gender, diabetes, CRP, albuminuria, and renin-angiotensin system blockers use. Despite these promising results, further clinical trials are necessary to support the role of uric acid lowering in renal disease progression. Only then, hypouricemic medical treatment could be widely used in daily clinical practice, especially since allopurinol treatment may be complicated by kidney toxicity and even the potentially fatal Stevens-Johnson syndrome.

Studies in CKD and diabetic kidney disease

Siu et al.^[39] reported that allopurinol therapy slowed renal disease progression in hyperuricemic subjects with modest (stage 3) CKD at 1 year compared to control groups. In a 4-month study, Momeni et al reported that allopurinol therapy could reduce proteinuria in subjects with diabetic kidney disease but without an effect on creatinine^[45].

In a meta-analysis, Wang et al.^[46] reported that uric acid lowering is associated with significant lowering of the serum creatinine concentration and an increase of the eGFR.

In the J-HEALTH study^[47], involving 7629 subjects, an alteration in the eGFR was correlated negatively with a change in the serum uric acid level and associated with less cardiovascular events.

Talaat and El-Sheikh performed a study whereby they withdrew allopurinol in subjects with CKD. In this study, there was a significant deterioration in blood pressure, proteinuria, and GFR in those subjects who were not receiving ACE inhibitors^[38].

While these studies mean that decreasing the uric acid level may simply be another way to block the RAAS, there is also some proof that such a lowering may have other benefits in addition to RAAS blockade^[48]. One special feature of the angiotensin receptor blocker, losartan is that it also lowers the serum uric acid level. There are now a few reports that the lowering of uric acid by losartan may provide additional benefits for slowing renal disease^[49] and reducing cardiovascular events^[50].

In RENAAL study, Miao et al. found that renal events, i.e. doubling of serum creatinine or end-stage renal disease, were less frequent in individuals in whom—as a result of the known uricosuric effect of losartan—serum uric acid concentrations were lowered by >0.5 mg/dL compared with patients with lesser lowering or increase (9.5 versus 14.3 events per 100 patient/years). The risk of renal events was reduced by 6% for every 0.5 mg/dL decrease in serum uric acid^[49].

Uric acid and its influence on renal transplantation

Hyperuricemia is a common complication in organ transplant recipients, and usually associated with chronic cyclosporine immunosuppressive therapy.

Risk factors for hyperuricemia include

1. decreased GFR,
2. diuretic use, and
3. preexistent history of hyperuricemia.

Most studies are in favour of an influence of uric acid on graft function and survival .But there are exceptions too; Meier-Kriesche et al.^[51]. taking their data from the SYMPHONY Study, in which a group of 1645 was followed-up for 3 years, found that the association of baseline uric acid with follow-up e-GFR, disappeared when adjusting for baseline e-GFR In the study by Haririan et al. after a mean 68-month follow-up, found out that hyperuricemia was associated with a 1.26 (95%CI: 1.03-1.53) hazard ratio of graft loss.^[52]

Conclusion

Uric acid, the end product of purine metabolism, can act as an anti-oxidant as well as a pro-oxidant. The main pathophysiological mechanisms responsible for uric acid-induced damage are endothelial dysfunction, activation of RAAS, increased oxidative stress and

proinflammatory and proliferative effects. Clinical studies and experimental studies have shown that uric acid does indeed lead to CKD progression, directly or indirectly. But larger and longer interventional clinical trials are required to elucidate the role of uric acid in the genesis and progression of renal disease and to confirm whether uric acid is a treatable factor for prevention and inhibition of renal and cardiovascular disease.

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There are no conflicts of interest to declare.